

MICROMECHANICS OF RECYCLED COMPOSITES FOR MATERIAL OPTIMISATION AND ECO-DESIGN

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1 Introduction

With the exponential growth in carbon-fibre (CF) use (Fig. 1) and, as a result, in CF Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) waste, recycling routes for CFRPs are now imperative [1]. This work aims to introduce *recycled* (r-) CFRPs in structural applications, by setting a framework for optimisation and eco-design with these novel materials.

Recycling will offset the considerable energy required for production of CFs (Fig. 2), which is currently their major drawback [2]. Life-Cycle Analyses (LCA) in transports industries are conclusive of the benefits of CFRPs in the *use phase* (Fig. 3). However, LCA shows that the life cycle of CFs needs to be extended further after their primary application, so as to offset the impact of the *production phase* [3-4]. Adding the effect of EoL legislation, CFRP recycling is now one of the most important issues for exploitation of CFRP in many industries, e.g. automotive [1].

Currently, technologies for recovering high-quality recycled fibres from CFRP waste are becoming mature, as proven by a few industrial-scale recycling operations and the consistent production of rCFRPs with compelling structural performances [1]. It is now fundamental to establish high-value markets for the recyclates by triggering their use in non-safety critical

secondary structures. This raises a formidable challenge, as the recyclates form a whole new type of material, with a unique mechanical response.

Using rCFRPs in structural applications requires that engineers are confident on their performance and have suitable design tools. However, the mechanical response of the recyclates diverges from that of their virgin precursors, as the recycling process may alter fibre properties, leave traces of residual virgin matrix on their surface, and result into a complex multiscale architecture of the composite (Fig. 4) [5].

This work presents a study on the mechanical response of rCFRPs (Fig. 5), aiming to:

- (i) understand their failure micro-mechanisms and how these are influenced by the recycling process;
- (ii) develop analytical models to predict the rCFRP's mechanical properties. These are to be used by recyclers for tailoring material optimisation, and by engineers in structural design with rCFRPs.

This paper focuses on the analysis of toughening mechanisms and fracture toughness prediction. This is motivated by the relevance of these features in crash-worthy components, which – as shown by several rCFRP automotive demonstrators manufactured [1] – are a credible target application for the recyclates. In addition, the multiscale features found in rCFRPs make toughness a challenging mathematical problem.

Fig. 1. Forecast for carbon fibre demand [1].

Fig. 2. Estimated ranges for energy consumption for material production [1-2].

Fig. 3. Environmental impact of a car's use-phase for different body-in-white materials [3-4].

In this paper, Section 2 summarises the experimental analysis of rCFRPs, which forms the physical basis for model development and validation in Section 3. The outcomes of this work are discussed in Section 4, and the main conclusions summarised in Section 5.

2 Experimental analysis of recycled CFRP

2.1 Materials and experimental procedures

Three different rCFRPs (\mathcal{A} , \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{C}) were thoroughly analysed experimentally; all materials had an epoxy resin reinforced by rCFs (reclaimed by pyrolysis) in a discontinuous and multidirectional architecture. The reinforcement scales (from single fibres to large bundles) were very different in all materials, due to the different recycling routes used (Table 1).

The experimental study [5] covers a comprehensive set of procedures to fully characterise the recyclates at the micro, meso and macro scales, so as to provide an in-depth understanding for model development as well as providing the required input properties:

- Single Fibre Tensile Tests (SFTT) and Single Fibre Pull-Out tests, for mechanical characterisation of fibres and fibre-resin interfaces;
- Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) of fibres, for morphology and diameter characterisation;
- Optical Microscopy (OM) of rCFRP samples for studying the reinforcement architecture, including the statistical characterisation of length, orientation and width distributions of fibres and bundles;

Fig. 4. rCFRP multiscale reinforcement, featuring dispersed fibres – originated from clean rCFs – and large bundles – held together by residual matrix [5].

- Mechanical testing of rCFRP, for characterisation of elastic properties and strength;
- Compact Tension (CT) tests, for measurement of fracture toughness and R-curves for the rCFRPs;
- Analysis of failure and toughening mechanisms, using in-situ OM and fracture surface SEM.

2.2 Experimental results

Single-fibre analyses showed very mild effects of the pyrolysis process, as the rCF performance was close to that of the virgin (v-) precursors (fibre morphology in Fig. 4, fibre strength in Fig. 6). The rCFRPs also compared well with Aluminium and phenolic Glass-Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) (Fig. 7).

The rCFRPs featured multiscale reinforcements (Fig. 4) ranging from $\text{\O}5 \mu\text{m}$ rCFs to 7 mm wide bundles. As shown by width Cumulative Density Functions (CDFs, Fig. 8), material \mathcal{A} had most fibres dispersed, while material \mathcal{C} featured the widest bundles.

The CT tests showed bundles arresting crack growth and locally toughening the rCFRPs through pull-out and defibrillation (Fig. 9). As architectures get coarser ($\mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{B} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$), fracture surfaces become more irregular, crack propagation stabilises, and the rCFRP toughness increases considerably.

The analysis of failure and toughening mechanisms showed self-similar features throughout the scales: fibres and bundles are similarly pulled-out (Fig. 10), and the defibrillation within fibre bundles presents stochastic fractal patterns (Fig. 11).

Fig. 5. Overall methodology for the analysis of recycled composites for material optimisation and eco-design.

Table 1: Description of the rCFRPs analysed

rCFRP	Waste source	Recycler	Remanufacturer	Fibre type	Matrix type
\mathcal{A}	Manuf. waste	RCF Ltd	U. Nottingham	Toray T300	ACG MTM57
\mathcal{B}	Manuf. waste	MIT	Boeing	Toray T300	HexFlow RTM 6
\mathcal{C}	EoL component	MIT	Boeing	Toray T800	HexFlow RTM 6

2.3 Discussion of experimental analysis

Three state-of-the-art rCFRPs were analysed, providing quantitative data and original observations – such as the multiscale and self-similar nature of the failure process in these materials.

The multiscale microstructure (Fig. 4, 8) induced by recycling is a unique rCFRP feature. Virgin short-fibre composites present reinforcements either mainly dispersed or in tows [6].

Two main toughening mechanisms were observed: *pull-out* (Fig. 10) and *defibrillation* (Fig. 11); while both have been reported for virgin CFRPs [7-9], rCFRPs are unique in that these processes occur over a wide range of scales in a self-similar manner.

Fig. 6. T300 fibre strength distributions: experimental results and Weibull fitting.

Fig. 7. Specific stiffness and strength of rCFRPs and competing virgin materials (material \mathcal{A} is anisotropic).

Fig. 8. Width distributions of reinforcing units (fibres and bundles).

a) rCFRP \mathcal{A}

b) rCFRP \mathcal{B}

c) rCFRP \mathcal{C}

Fig. 9. R-curves mapped with the fracture surfaces (results are representative of all specimens tested).

a) Fibre scale

b) Bundle scale

Fig. 10. Multiscale pull-out [5].

Fig. 11. Stochastic self-similarity in fracture of bundles [5].

3 Micromechanical modelling

3.1 Model development

3.1.1 Methodology

Based on the experimental results, a micromechanical model for the toughness of rCFRPs is here proposed. The model considers a crack propagating over an area A_c , *pulling out* or *fracturing* every Reinforcing Unit (RU, fibres and bundles) it crosses. Energy dissipated in either process – W_{po} and W_F , probability \mathcal{P}_{po} and \mathcal{P}_F – is calculated, and integrated over the microstructure (domain Ω) to give the fracture toughness (\mathcal{G}_{rCFRP}):

$$\mathcal{G}_{rCFRP} = 1/A_c \cdot \int (\mathcal{P}_{po} \cdot W_{po} + \mathcal{P}_F \cdot W_F) d\Omega \quad (1)$$

3.1.2 Pull-out work of reinforcing units (W_{po})

The model for W_{po} (Fig. 12) assumes a unilaterally debonded RU (length l_{po}), being pulled-out at an angle φ from an elastic foundation with stiffness k_e . The pulled-out length s_{po} is progressively increased, until either the RU is completely pulled ($s_{po}^{max} = l_{po}$, $\beta=0$) or fails during the process (at $s_{po}^{max} < l_{po}$, $\beta=1$). Four energy dissipation sources are considered:

- *Friction* (coefficient μ) due to residual interfacial stresses at the fibre-matrix interface, $p_{f/m}^{\Delta T}$. This acts along the RU's effective perimeter C_{RU} , generating a pull-out force:

$$P_{\mu}^{\Delta T} = \mu \cdot C_{RU} \cdot p_{f/m}^{\Delta T} \cdot (l_{po} - s_{po}) \quad (2)$$

- *Friction due to the snubbing effect* [8] from the RU's deflection $v(x)$ on the foundation (Fig. 12b). This creates a distributed force $q(x) = -k_e \cdot v(x)$ on the supported side, generating a pull-out force:

$$P_{\mu}^q = \mu \cdot k_e \cdot \xi \int_{x=0}^{l_{emb}} |q(x)| dx \quad (3)$$

where ξ results from the sinusoidal distribution of contact stresses on the RU's surface.

- *Sudden release of bending energy* at the end of pull-out. This is represented by:

$$W_e = j \int_{\delta_i=0}^{\delta} -E_{RU}^1 \cdot I_{RU} \cdot v^{(3)}(l_{emb}) \Big|_{\delta=\delta_i} d\delta_i \quad (4)$$

where $j = 1$ for complete pull-out (Fig. 12c) or $j = 2$ for RU failure during pull-out (Fig. 12b).

- *Fracture energy of the RU* ($W_{F,po}$), included if the RU maximum stresses reach its strength ($\beta=1$).

Finally, the pull-out work of a RU is given by:

$$W_{po} = \int_0^{s_{po}^{max}} (P_{\mu}^{\Delta T} + P_{\mu}^q) ds_{po} + W_e + \beta \cdot W_{F,po} \quad (5)$$

3.1.3 Fracture of reinforcing units

The multiscale rCFRP architecture promotes a size effect in the strength and toughness of RUs; these may fail before debonding (with a probability $\beta_F = 1 - \beta_{po}$) or during the pull-out.

Weibull's theory – with associated fibre strength distribution $\mathcal{P}_0^U(\sigma, l)$ [10] – is here extended to the analysis of embedded fibres. In a discontinuous CFRP with a plastic interface (strength S_{IF}), the stress field in a fibre during debonding is linear, so the strength distribution of the debonding fibre is:

$$\mathcal{P}_0^L(\sigma, l) = 1 - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\prod_{i=1}^n \left[1 - \mathcal{P}_0^U \left(\frac{i\sigma}{n}, \frac{l}{n} \right) \right] \right) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 12. Pull-out model for reinforcing units (fibres or bundles).

Fig. 13. Strength scaling model: sequence of fibre failures leading to level-1 bundle failure.

Fig. 14. Idealised stochastic fractal fracture surface of bundles.

Fig. 15. Geometric model for integration of energies over the rCFRP's architecture.

Expanding Eq. 6, the probability of fibre failure before debonding (p_F in Eq. 1) becomes:

$$p_F(l_{po}) = 1 - \exp \left[-\frac{2 \cdot l_{po}}{m+1} \left(\frac{c_f \cdot S_{IF} \cdot l_{po}}{A_f \cdot X_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (7)$$

For scaling the strength of fibres to bundles, an extension of a hierarchical model for *dry* bundles [11] is proposed. The main original contribution is the inclusion of a plastic matrix, which results into (i) stress concentrations around a break being limited to the recovery length l_i (Fig. 13), and (ii) only fibre breaks closer than $2 l_i$ result in final bundle failure.

The strength distribution of a level-1 bundle is derived from the failure sequence of its 2 fibres (Fig. 13); a hierarchical failure process is then continued, until the entire bundle section has failed (Fig. 14).

3.1.4 Integration over the reinforcement architecture

The probabilities for the variables in the integration domain $\Omega = \{(l_{po}, \varphi, w)\}$ are related to the experimentally measured Probability Density Functions (PDFs) of length, orientation and width of RUs – respectively $p(l)$, $p(\psi)$ and $p(w)$ (Fig. 15):

$$\begin{cases} p(l_{po}, l) = 2 \cos \varphi \cdot p(l)/w_c, & 0 < l_{po} \leq l/2 \\ p(\varphi) = p(\psi + \alpha), & -\pi/2 < \varphi \leq \pi/2 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Assuming l , ψ and w to be independent, then:

$$d\Omega = N_{RU} p(l_{po}, l) p(\varphi) p(w) dl_{po} dl d\varphi dw \quad (9)$$

The total number of RUs in the composite (N_{RU}) is related to the reinforcement fraction V_{RU} by [6]:

$$V_{RU} = (N_{RU} \cdot \bar{A} \cdot \bar{l}) / (\Delta a \cdot t_s \cdot w_s) \quad (10)$$

Substituting Eq. 8-10 in Eq. 1 fully defines the integration scheme for calculating G_{rCFRP} .

3.2 Modelling results

The predictions for fibre pull-out work ($l_{po} = 50 \mu\text{m}$, varying orientations φ) are shown in Fig. 16, together with literature [7] and FE (Fig. 17) results.

The results from the hierarchical fracture model for the effect of filament count in bundle strength are shown in Fig. 18. As the bundle size increases, both the average strength and the variability are reduced.

Analytical and experimental fracture toughness results are compared in Fig. 19. Parametric studies are shown in Fig. 19b for the coefficient of friction μ , and in Fig. 20 for micromechanical fibre properties.

Fig. 16. Predictions for fibre pull-out work: analytical model vs. FE and literature [6] results.

Fig. 17. Detail of the Finite Elements (FE) analysis for validation of the pull-out model.

Fig. 18. Strength distributions for bundles with different filament counts.

a) Experimental R-curves and predictions

b) Anisotropy of experimental results and modelling predictions for rCFRP A

Fig. 20. Sensitivity study on the effect of fibre properties at the toughness of rCFRP C.

Fig. 19. Model predictions vs. experimental results.

4 Discussion

Following an extensive experimental investigation, an analytical model to predict the fracture toughness of multiscale rCFRPs was developed. This was based on the *pull-out* and *fracture* of fibres and bundles, acting over the entire range of *reinforcement scales*.

The new pull-out model was able to capture the response predicted by very complex 3D FE models (Fig. 16 and 17), showing an improvement over literature models [7]. The hierarchical scaling laws proposed for the strength of fibres and bundles (Fig. 18) also reproduce the response reported for virgin composites [10], and extend the applicability of dry fibre bundle models [11] to composites.

These new approaches – and their novel combination in a multiscale model – were applied to the rCFRPs studied. Comparing the predictions with experimental results is extremely encouraging, as toughnesses one order of magnitude apart are reproduced accurately by the model (Fig. 19a). For the anisotropic material \mathcal{A} (Fig. 19b), the model is able to capture the variation of toughness with crack orientation (α).

Several sensitivity studies were performed. The fibre-matrix friction coefficient (μ) is key for the toughness of dispersed rCFRPs (\mathcal{A} , Fig. 19b), while fibre strength is critical for coarser materials (\mathcal{C} , Fig. 20).

5 Conclusions

This paper presented in-depth analysis and modelling of toughening mechanisms of rCFRPs.

The experimental programme revealed a unique and complex multiscale architecture in the recyclates, with a critical role on their mechanical response. This study showed that residual matrix is not necessarily a recycling defect, as it actually enhances the fracture toughness of rCFRPs. A thorough characterisation, showing properties consistently reaching those of conventional materials and detailing load transfer and failure mechanisms, is raising confidence on rCFRPs within the industry, especially the automotive one.

A physically-based analytical model, which provides a unique tool for the prediction of properties of the recyclates, was developed. The focus on the fracture toughness, while requiring many challenging features – e.g. a frictional pull-out model, strength scaling laws, integration over a multiscale architecture – can support the optimisation of recycling processes towards crash-worthy materials, and their application for eco-design of non-safety-critical structures.

Further development of design methodologies, together with quality control of recycling processes, are now vital for the application of rCFRPs in structural components. Overcoming these challenges will firmly establish the recyclates as green and high-performance materials, and finally close the loop in the CFRP life-cycle.

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